

Chromium(VI) in tannery effluents : assessment, biodistribution and environmental health impact

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Abstract : The concentration of chromium(VI) [Cr^{VI}] in the effluent, sludge, soil of the agricultural field and water from the wetland around the sites of tannery industries was measured by instrumental methods. There is a decline in chromium concentration in effluent as a function of distance travelled by it while reverse trend is observed in case of sludge. Results indicate that there is a substantial buildup of Cr^{VI} in the soils of agricultural field which is irrigated by the tannery effluent, as compared to the controlled soil sample. Wetlands are also contaminated as tannery effluent and sludge are used as food for fishes. Consumption of food crops and fish contaminated with heavy metals is a major food chain route for human exposure. We studied the health risks of Cr^{VI} in contaminated food crops irrigated with tannery effluent as well as fish cultured in Cr^{VI} contaminated wetlands. The concentration of chromium in plants grown in tannery effluent-irrigated soils and in tissues of the fish is much higher than their respective controlled samples. The study highlights that both adults and children consuming food crops grown in effluent-irrigated soils and the fish cultured in contaminated wetland, ingest significant amount of the metal.

Keywords : Chromium(VI), bioaccumulation, biological concentration factor, pollution load index, daily intake of metals, health risk index.

Introduction

Heavy metals are ubiquitous in the environment, as a result of both natural and anthropogenic activities, and humans are exposed to them through various pathways¹. These metals are extremely toxic and it is readily mobilized by human activities such as mining and dumping industrial waste in natural habitats such as forests, rivers, lakes, and ocean². These discharge of toxic trace metals in water bodies cause metal assimilation in aquatic animals³. The untreated industrial waste is widely used in agriculture either as manure in the production of vegetables or as liquid sewage as a source of water for irrigation, and again as a feed for fish bred in the wetland areas and ponds⁴. Some environmental risks are always associated with these industrial effluent fed farming and aquaculture.

The heavy metal like Cr^{VI}, an essential component of the tanning process, is coming out with the effluent of tannery industry. This effluent is an important source of nutrient to vegetables and fish. Chromium has been considered as one of the top 16th toxic pollutants and be-

cause of its carcinogenic and teratogenic characteristics on the public, it has become a serious health concern. Though chromium exists in nine valency states ranging from -2 to +6, Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} are of major environmental significance. Cr^{VI} is more mobile and toxic than Cr^{III}⁵. In the present study concentration of Cr^{VI} in the tannery effluent and sludge was estimated. Bioaccumulation of Cr in vegetables grown in tannery effluent irrigated soil and waste water fed fish was determined and the associated health risks due to the consumption of these foods were assessed.

Results

Estimation of Cr^{VI} in tannery effluent and sludge :

The contamination of total Cr, Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} in tannery effluent and sludge at four stations is presented in Table 1 while the same for soil of affected agricultural land and water of wetland is presented in the Table 2.

Bioaccumulation study of Cr in vegetables and fish :

The Pollution load index (PLI) of the water samples collected from the wetland area was 1.87. The concentra-

Table 1. Level of Cr in effluent and sludge

Station	Concentration of Cr in effluent (mg/L)			Concentration of Cr in sludge (mg/L)		
	(n = 4)			(n = 4)		
	Total Cr	Cr ^{VI}	Cr ^{III}	Total Cr	Cr ^{VI}	Cr ^{III}
I	188.82 ± 2.261	26.11 ± 3.293	162.71 ± 1.504	2976.55 ± 71.436	2530.08 ± 62.575	446.47 ± 58.442
II	113.67 ± 4.3417	17.00 ± 2.173	96.67 ± 4.712	3149.14 ± 84.538	2676.96 ± 82.690	472.18 ± 38.395
III	67.78 ± 1.884	10.08 ± 2.092	57.70 ± 2.0366	3237.48 ± 58.963	2800.00 ± 50.483	437.48 ± 60.888
IV	53.86 ± 3.929363	8.07 ± 0.650	45.78 ± 3.790	3328.47 ± 35.633	2829.20 ± 30.288	499.27 ± 5.345

Table 2. Level of Cr in soil and water

Type of sample	Concentration of Cr in contaminated sample (mg/L) (test sample)			Concentration of Cr in non-contaminated sample (mg/L) (controlled)			PLI
	Total Cr	Cr ^{VI}	Cr ^{III}	Total Cr	Cr ^{VI}	Cr ^{III}	
	Concentration of Cr in soil at 15 cm depth (n = 8)	123.30 ± 4.757	106.74 ± 4.137	16.02 ± 0.620	34.66 ± 3.036	30.14 ± 2.640	
Concentration of Cr in soil at 30 cm depth (n = 8)	85.33 ± 4.448	74.20 ± 3.867	11.13 ± 0.580	28.44 ± 2.815	24.74 ± 2.448	3.71 ± 0.367	2.99
Concentration of Cr in water (n = 4)	0.056 ± 0.009	0.030 ± 0.005	0.025 ± 0.004	0.029 ± 0.003	0.016 ± 0.002	0.013 ± 0.001	1.87

Table 3. The concentration of Cr in the edible portions of vegetables and fish of wetland area and the pollution load index (PLI)

Type of vegetables	Type of samples	Concentration of Cr (mg/L)			PLI
		Leaf	Range	Mean ± S.D.	
Cauliflower (<i>Brassica bortrytis</i>) (n = 8)	Non-contaminated (control)	Leaf	Range	0.18–0.28	3.83
			Mean ± S.D.	0.24 ± 0.032	
	Flower	Range	BDL		
		Mean ± S.D.			
	Contaminated (test sample)	Leaf	Range	0.85–0.98	
			Mean ± S.D.	0.92 ± 0.043	
Flower	Range	0.19–0.25			
	Mean ± S.D.	0.24 ± 0.041			
Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleraceae</i>) (n = 8)	Non-contaminated (controlled)	Range	1.81–2.42	4.45	
		Mean ± S.D.	2.14 ± 0.235		
	Contaminated (test sample)	Range	8.81–9.82		
		Mean ± S.D.	9.36 ± 0.289		
Tilapia (<i>Tilapia mossambica</i>) (n = 4)	Non-contaminated (controlled)	Range	0.041–0.053	2.08	
		Mean ± S.D.	0.048 ± 0.005		
	Contaminated (test sample)	Range	0.08–0.12		
		Mean ± S.D.	0.1 ± 0.018		
Bata (<i>Labio bata</i>) (n = 8)	Non-contaminated (controlled)	Range	0.045–0.05	2.08	
		Mean ± S.D.	0.048 ± 0.002		
	Contaminated (test sample)	Range	0.07–0.13		
		Mean ± S.D.	0.1 ± 0.027		

Note : BDL = Below Detection Level.

tion of Cr in two different types of vegetables such as cauliflower (*Brassica bortrytis*) and spinach (*Spinacia oleraceae*) are presented in the Table 3. The Biological

concentration factor (BCF) values of Cr in both vegetables and fish samples are presented in the Table 4. The estimated Daily intake of metals (DIM) through the food

Table 4. Biological concentration factor (BCF) of Cr in vegetables and fishes

Types of samples (vegetables/fishes)	BCF of non-contaminated (control) sample		BCF of contaminated (test) sample	
	Leaf	Flower	Leaf	Flower
Cauliflower (<i>Brassica bortrytis</i>)	0.0079 ± 0.0015	-	0.0086 ± 0.0002	0.0024 ± 0.0002
Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleraceae</i>)	0.069 ± 0.011		0.087 ± 0.0005	
Tilapia (<i>Tilapia mossambica</i>)	2.8 ± 0.490		3.35 ± 0.788	
Bata (<i>Labio bata</i>)	3.0 ± 0.381		3.44 ± 1.037	

Table 5. The estimated DIM through the food chain and the corresponding HRI of adults and children

Samples	DIM (mg/kg/person day)		HRI	
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children
Leaf of cauliflower (<i>Brassica bortrytis</i>)	4.82×10^{-4}	5.54×10^{-4}	0.16	0.18
Flower of cauliflower (<i>Brassica bortrytis</i>)	1.25×10^{-4}	1.44×10^{-4}	0.041	0.048
Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleraceae</i>)	4.91×10^{-3}	5.64×10^{-3}	1.63	1.88
Tilapia (<i>Tilapia mossambica</i>)	4.29×10^{-3}	7.33×10^{-5}	0.014	0.024
Bata (<i>Labio bata</i>)	4.29×10^{-3}	7.33×10^{-5}	0.014	0.024

chain and the corresponding Health risk index (HRI) of adults and children are presented in Table 5.

Discussion

These results indicate that there occurs a decline in chromium concentration in effluent as a function of distance while reverse trend is observed in case of sludge.

In the tannery effluent-irrigated soils and in the wetland where tannery effluent and sludge used as the food for fish, Cr concentrations were significantly higher compared to their respective controlled samples. PLI of Cr in soil and water from wetland which represents the number of times by which the heavy metal concentration in soils and fish at particular horizon exceeds the background concentration⁶. In this study area, soil contamination with metals is mainly due to the irrigation by the tannery effluent, application of sludge in the farmlands, and possible atmospheric deposition. The PLI of soil samples indicates that rate of accumulation of Cr at surface of the soil

is greater as compared to the deep soil and therefore, hazardous to plant biomass⁷. The wetlands are contaminated by tannery effluent and sludge as these are used as feed for the fish. The PLI values of vegetables and fish samples indicate high degree of contamination in the samples.

The bioaccumulation of environmental pollutants in aquatic and terrestrial biota is quantified with the assumption that organisms achieve a chemical equilibrium with respect to a particular media or route of exposure⁸ and expressed with the help of 'Biological concentration factor'. Typically, the soil-to-plant and water to fish transfer factors are one of the key components of human exposure to metals through the food chain.

The high transfer values for Cr from soil to vegetables indicate a strong accumulation of the respective metals by food crops, particularly by leafy vegetables⁹. The above mentioned analysis indicates that the accumulation of metal is higher in the water containing body part. The rate of

transfer of Cr in both types of fish samples are the same.

The above discussion indicates that some toxic heavy metal like Cr become concentrated instead of dispersed in the food chain. The accumulation of heavy metal like Cr in the food chain depends to a great extent on the environmental condition.

In order to assess the health risk of any chemical pollutant, it is essential to estimate the level of exposure by quantifying the routes of exposure of a pollutant to the target organisms. There are various possible exposure pathways of pollutants to humans but the food chain is one of the most important pathways. As the tannery induced Cr contaminated vegetables and fish produced in the study area are mostly sold in the local urban market, therefore, the average metal concentrations of vegetables and fish were used for calculation of the HRI. The determination of DIM is also required to calculate the HRI.

The data of HRI values were < 1 except in spinach. Therefore, the health risks due to chromium(VI), exposure through the food chain is not very significant except in case of spinach. Although the findings of this study regarding DIM and HRI suggest that the consumption of plants, except spinach, grown in wastewater-contaminated soils and the fish cultured in wetland contaminated by tannery effluent and sludge could be considered to be less hazardous, but there are also other sources of metal exposures such as dust inhalation, dermal contact and ingestion (for children) of metal contaminated soils, which were not included in this study. The HRI value of consumption of spinach for both adult and children was > 1 . So, the frequent consumption of spinach, collected from the affected agricultural land could cause severe problems as Cr^{VI} poses a health risk. Hexavalent chromium is considered extremely toxic (causing liver damage, dermatitis and gastrointestinal ulcers), mutagenic and carcinogenic¹⁰.

Experimental

Study area :

Effluent and sludge samples were collected from Tannery Complex of Kolkata, India. The vegetables and wastewater irrigated soil were collected from adjoining agricultural fields. Fish and water samples were collected from local wetland areas which were again fed by the

above mentioned wastes.

Sampling and treatment of different samples :

Tannery effluent samples were collected from four different sampling stations, which are located 0.05 km (station I), 0.25 km (station II), 0.5 km (station III) and 0.75 km (station IV) away respectively from the last discharge point of tannery complex. In case of sludge, around 3 kg of wet sludge was collected from four previously described sampling stations. 0.5 g of wet sludge was taken from the estimation and suspended in triple distilled water.

Samples of soil were collected from two different depths (15 cm and 30 cm) of the agricultural field which is irrigated by tannery effluent while the water samples were collected from the four different adjoining wetlands.

Two types of vegetables cauliflower (*Brassica botrytis*) and spinach (*Spinacia oleraceae*) were collected from the same sites where soils. In case of cauliflower, the leaves as well as flowers were considered while only the leaf part of spinach was taken for the experiment. Two types of fish (*Labio bata* and *Tilapia mossambica*) were sampled from same wetland area from where water samples were collected.

Analysis of the samples :

The Cr^{VI} concentrations in the effluent, sludge, soil and water samples were determined spectrophotometrically at 540 nm after complexation with 1,5-diphenylcarbazide¹¹ using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-3410) and compared it with the standard curve. The concentration of total Cr in other samples including effluent and sludge were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Quality control of the samples :

The quality control of the samples was performed by comparing with the determined value of Cr in the respective non contaminated samples.

Biological concentration factor (BCF) :

The biomagnification of pollutants in aquatic and terrestrial biota may be expressed with the help of BCF. BCF was calculated as follows :

$$\text{BCF} = \frac{\text{Concentration of metal in organism}}{\text{Concentration of metal in environment}}$$

Pollution load index (PLI) :

The degree of pollution by metal was measured using the PLI technique. The following modified equation was used to assess the PLI level in different segments of environment.

$$PLI = \frac{\text{Concentration of metal in samples}}{\text{Concentration of metal in controlled samples}}$$

Daily intake of metals (DIM) :

The DIM was determined by the following equation.

$$DIM = \frac{C_{\text{metal}} \times C_{\text{factor}} \times D_{\text{food intake}}}{B_{\text{average weight}}}$$

where, C_{metal} = heavy metals concentrations in vegetables and fish (mg kg^{-1}), C_{factor} = conversion factor = 0.085 and 0.16 was used to convert fresh weight to dry for vegetables and fish respectively, as described by Rattan *et al.*¹², $D_{\text{food intake}}$ = daily intake of vegetables or fish = 0.345 and 0.232 $\text{kg person}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (average intake of vegetables for adult and children) = 0.150 $\text{kg person}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (average intake of fish for both adult and children)¹³ and $B_{\text{average weight}}$ = average body weight, respectively = 55.9 and 32.7 kg (adult and children respectively)¹⁴.

Health risk index (HRI) :

The HRI for the locals through the consumption of contaminated vegetables was assessed based on the DIM and the reference oral dose (RfD). The RfD for chromium(VI) as previously reported is 0.003 mg/kg/day ¹⁵, $HRI = DIM/RfD$ ⁹.

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